

HOW TO PROVIDE QUALITY TEACHING ENVIRONMENT IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES: BANGLADESH CASE

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Abstract:

Achieving inclusive and quality education for all, we strongly believe that education is one of the most powerful and proven vehicles for sustainable development. Conscious dreams are the result of weird mathematical manipulation of our daily life. We see a dream that, one day the education system of Bangladesh will be on the right track. On 16th December 1971 Bangladesh after getting independent from suppression, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, the father of the Nation had a dream to build a successful nation, namely Shonar Bangla. For doing the same, it was necessary to build an educated nation not only by producing Dr., Engineers, and Teachers but also by producing effective practical knowledgeable human resources. To formulate an effective education policy, different government formed different commission but, due to some invisible reason, no commission got materialized. In this current conceptual paper, we will be focusing on Bangladeshi educational institute and, education policies, to find out the obstacles behind providing quality teaching and effective learning.

Keywords: education policy; quality teaching; effective learning; national stability; Bangladesh

1. Introduction

In 2016 Prime Minister of people's republic of Bangladesh Sheikh Hasina daughter of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahaman, the father of the Nation, announced bringing out Higher Educations reforms to establish at least one university or sub-campus at district level across the country for promotion of higher education[1-2]. A total of 95 private universities have permission to run educational programs in the country under the Private University Act-2010, and 89 universities are in operation private at present.

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There are only two international universities in Bangladesh. They are neither managed nor funded by the government, like public universities, nor established under the Private University Act and managed by a private governing body, like private universities. International Culture University, established by civil society organization and branded by United Nations Academic Impact (UNAI) [3-5] and United Nations Global Compact (UNGC) [5], is an internationally accredited-affiliated and an active partner of different international organizations working for internationalization of education and international quality. Islamic University of Technology was established by the Organization of Islamic Cooperation and is located in Gazipur, Dhaka division, while another is located in Chittagong division and funded by the Asian University for Women Support Foundation (AUWSF), a United States-based non-profit corporation.

Being enormously populated country, it's hard to provide quality education to its citizen, beside that lack of quality teacher will make the situation more convoluted and education system will certainly become more fragile. However, this acerbic situation can be assuaged by making sure that some absolute compact decisions are being implemented properly with care. Public-private cooperation are pre-required to established an effective educational institute and also need to make sure that teacher are always there for their students. From the beginning of 2000, people from private sector were come forward to facilitate higher education for all, but that was just business, enough steps were not taken to monitor these institutes to make sure about providing quality education. All of a certain huge number of graduates were become the burden of the nation, and they were not properly educated and trained to be able to fight in the arena of job market. After 2009 some private Universities took measures to provide quality education, but the thing was that, still majorities' of our child's were not able to get chances to get admitted in these institutes because number of quality based higher education providing institute was very few, and we have to think pensively, and then we see how expensive these organizations are, and that are not for the middle class peoples. Since after the establishment of more government higher educational institutes with the cooperation of private sectors by creating private opportunities for higher education, now there are at least institutes are there for providing higher education. It's now up to the government to take the best care of these educational institutes to make sure, that, from there students will get quality and effective education.

2. Education Commission and Educational Policies of Bangladesh

Although Bangladesh has existed as an independent country only since the late 20th century, its national character within a broader South Asian context dates to the ancient past. The country's history, then, is intertwined with that of India, Pakistan, and other countries of the area. The land of Bangladesh, mainly a delta formed by the Padma (Ganges [Ganga]) and the Jamuna (Brahmaputra) rivers in the northeastern portion of the Indian subcontinent, is protected by forests to the west and a myriad of watercourses in the centre. As such, it was long the inaccessible frontier beyond the north Indian plain and therefore was home to a distinctive regional culture. In early

times a number of independent principalities flourished in the region – called Bengal – including Gangaridai, Vanga, Gauda, Pundra, and Samatata, among others. In the 14th century, Shamsuddin Ilyas Shah was instrumental in unifying many of these principalities. The Mughals added more territories, including Bihar and Orissa (now states of India), to constitute Suba Bangalah, which the British colonial administration later called the Bengal Presidency. In 1947, when British colonial rule ended, a downsized province of Bengal was partitioned into East Bengal and West Bengal. East Bengal was renamed East Pakistan in 1955, and in 1971 it became Bangladesh by a bloody WAR against Pakistani armed force. During the war Bangladesh lost more than 3 million lives, more than 2,00,000-4,00,000 women were tortured and molested by Pakistani Armed Forces and their local collaborators Jamaat-e-Islami, Razakars, Al-Badar, Shanti Committee and Al-Shams and at least 3,00,000 children died at refugee camps due to malnutrition and diseases [6-8, 10, 11, 13-15]. To eliminate the future intellectual leaders of the new nation, Pakistani armed force killed 1,111 Academics, Journalist, Physicians, Lawyers, Litterateurs, Artists and Engineers [6, 9-12].

After becoming an independent country by getting all of these through, the founding father of Bangladesh Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahaman understood that we need a new Education Commission. On 26 July 1972 he formed a National Education Commission headed by an eminent educationist and scientist Dr. Quadrat-i-Khuda and was formally inaugurated on 24 September 1972 [14]. This commission is known as Quadrat-i-Khuda Education Commission and submitted its report to the government on 30 May 1974 by collecting opinions from the elitist people in the form of questionnaire, and after careful sorting of the opinions prepared a report suggesting reconstruction of the education system. This commission prepared a pro-people, modern and science oriented education policy. With the change of government system, begun with the diabolical murder of founding father Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahaman and his family members on 15 August, 1975, the education policy proposed by Quadrat-i-Khuda Education Commission was not implemented [13]. After that, so many commissions were formulated but not got implemented again.

2.1 Obstacles

We have to understand that access to education can improve the economic outcomes of citizens and determine the prospects of future generations, especially in developing countries. According to the constitution the Art17 stated that “*All the Children of Bangladesh are supposed to get full free education up to secondary level.*”(Article 17, 1998: 8 - 9). From 1972 to 2010 near about 40 years different education commission were formed and their main agenda for primary education were same as Art. 17, But the reality is very harsh, we have been experiencing that our child ages 5 to 15 are been working hard for arranging their livelihood. Even they are not getting proper food to live on, though certain groups of people are sending their children in very expensive educational institute just keeping intact their status. There is no balance in our society, one group of people is fighting for their very existence and other group of people are been fighting for their supremacy. Government is doing too little to assuage the

situation, and we also believe it is not only in the government hand. People from all class should realize the situation and work together to get it back in the right track. Some of the visible drawbacks are poor educational institute, not being able to provide effective and practical education, quality of student, gender inequality, income related inequality, poor education policies and its implementation, and not but the least *“the political inconsistency or harsh political situation, lack of respect towards each other.”*

To solve this problem and create an effective, equal opportunity for all, first we have to find out the obstacles behind providing quality teaching and effective learning environment. A development will not be sustainable if it is not ensure the participation of Government, private and people from civil society. If we had considered the goals of sustainable development, we could see that quality education is one of them. Achieving inclusive and quality education for all, reaffirms the belief that education is one of the most powerful and proven vehicles for sustainable development [16].

3. Discussion

One thing is very clear that everybody wants to keep his offspring happy and want a society where they can sustain peacefully and peace is a matter of entirely earned. If within the entire society people respect each other and respected governmental organization completely work for the betterment of the society then only peace will exist. Without proper education, we will not be able to achieve the sustainable society where we can live peacefully. Let us now consider the following conceptual model inspired by [1, 2, 17-20]:

Figure 1: Conceptual Model for Developing a Sound Educational Environment

Creating a sound environment for education is not only about making sound educational institutes, rather we have to work on how people thinking, how much we have respect for the country, how much mutual respect towards each other do we have, how much people want to develop their country, how much do we believe in Bangladeshi Nationality, lastly but not the least that how much respect do we have towards developing a sound and effective learning environment. Again, consider the following conceptual model towards the path for the effective educational environment inspired by [17, 19-21]:

Figure 2: Conceptual Model towards the Path for the Effective Educational Environment

4. Conclusion

People of our country should come on a common podium and think about a sustainable program which will ultimately make the path of creativity, better, and effective learning environment possible. Without developing creative thought, respect for mutual prosperity it would not be possible to make an environment where people can live independently. Without getting independent from this environment possibly, we will not be able to provide democratic political environment and which is the very important element in the path of creating national stability. When Bangladesh and countries like us will be able to create a national stability in the field of politics only then it would be possible to provide that heavenly environment in our education system. It is not a matter of creating policies year after year; it is completely about creating a state where people get enough respect for their individual independent creative thought. This is probably the high time for the people, policy maker, different stakeholder, development partner, and politician to focusing on Bangladeshi

educational institute and, education policies, to find out the obstacles behind providing quality teaching and effective learning.

Conflict of interest statement

We declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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